

Responsible Media and Media Literacy for Promoting Democracy in Nepal

Media literacy equips individuals with the skills to critically evaluate media content, recognize biases, and differentiate between credible information and misinformation. By promoting media literacy, society can better understand and engage with media content, making more informed decisions.

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Abstract

Since its early days, mass media has significantly contributed to promoting societal norms and eventually democratic values. As media is considered the fourth pillar of any functioning democracy, one cannot imagine a democracy without media which is there to inform people and hold those in power accountable. Likewise, media can only flourish in a democratic society where it is provided a favorable environment for thriving and functioning. In authoritarian regimes or undemocratic societies, media perish and shrink. But just allowing the number of media to open cannot ensure the democratic strength. For democracy to be strong enough citizen should have strong media literacy so that they can make informed and proper choice of media and its content. Media literacy among audiences is one of the most important condition for media responsibility. If media properly functions following the fundamental principles and ethical standards, then only democracy

can foster. And if people lack media literacy and media does not follow its responsibility, accountability and all ethical norms and values, the overall democratic process is always improper and questioned. When the need and importance of media is always questioned and massively criticized media loses credibility and public trust. Democracy itself becomes weaker when media in the society is unreliable. The chain of weakness is created on the way. Weak media construct weaker societies, weak public audience lacking media literacy let media be weaker. Media may become unethical, unprofessional, irresponsible and unaccountable if its audience hugely lack media literacy. Irresponsible media cannot hold the authorities in power accountable and the society further lacks good governance. Thus authority loose trust of the people. Then the state mechanism and system get interrupted. So, democracy needs media literate people and media is expected to strictly follow professionalism while functioning. Responsible media is also expected to contribute to strengthen the democracy within the country and all over the world.

Keywords

media, function, responsibility, promotion, participatory democracy, media literacy

Introduction

As human civilization evolved and humans started living in groups, they had to communicate for day-to-day survival, communicate with other communities, groups and outsiders. Signs, symbols, gestures, and postures were primarily used for exchanging and sharing messages. For several centuries, human civilizations relied on signs and symbols, or pictorial messages to convey their messages, even store messages and information for the future civilization. Gradually, verbal and written codes were used, and they turned into spoken and written languages. As time passed, men started to live in groups, they formed families, communities, and societies. With the advent of scripts, human society found language as a reliable means for communicating not

only among each other, within groups and communities, but also far-flung communities spread across oceans. And, the traditional forms of mass media came into existence. Wooden and metal block printing on animal's dry skin and clothes began. Paper and writing technologies were developed and used. However, it took human civilization several centuries to develop something that would truly make mass communication as we know it now possible. It was only in the mid-15th century when German citizen Johannes Gutenberg invented the movable printing press, making it possible to print and publish books or any other reading materials for mass distribution and storage. Modern printing technology revolutionized the modern mass media and communication culture as it paved the way for mass printing of books, newspapers, magazines, etc. For the next four centuries, the world witnessed massive publication of books, newspapers, magazines, pamphlets and posters across the world, contributing to mass communication and preserving the knowledge that was produced before and after the invention of the modern printing press. In the last quarter of the 19th century, the world witnessed another milestone as humans could transmit voice or audio messages across the oceans or physical distance. In the 1930s, the invention of a device that could transmit not only sound but also picture through a glaring box was seen as another miracle. which soon became famous as television. The arrival of radio, television and cinema aided mass culture and communication which changed human society forever. After Tim Berners Lee invented the World Wide Web (WWW) in 1990, it opened the door for online and social media. The development of technology has increased so rapidly in such a way that with the development of new media and social networks, the role and importance of media has been increasing exponentially which could never have been imagined earlier.

By informing, educating, entertaining, and persuading the people in society, the media enable them to actively participate in all the processes of the democratic system. In any country, media are considered social institutions that play a vital role

in promoting and enabling participatory democracy which ultimately strengthening democracy for all. And, as all mentioned, there is a strong bond and interrelationship between media and democracy. One cannot fully function in each other's absence. The relative relationship between media and democracy is so strong and inevitable that the absence or lack of one directly puts another in danger. Without media, a critical media, democracy can neither survive nor thrive. And, for making media more critical and responsible, media literacy among mass people must be developed. It is because media literate public can make media more professional and accountable and such media can properly function as a watchdog of a democratic society. Media literate people can make informed choices and it helps the people to participate in the democratic process. This is how bond between people, media and democracy becomes strong and participatory democracy develops.

Media and Society

“Society is a construct rather than a fixed reality. Media provide the materials for reality construction” (McQuail, 2005). According to McQuail mass media forms society through the contents it shares. Media are of several forms but news media is mostly discussed here which share news and views. “News is a timely presentation of media content among their audience including the information about the recent happenings of public importance. For prof. P. Kharel, “news is the first and foremost quality of any news media” (Kharel, 2006).

In general, the four major functions of mass media are to inform, educate, entertain, and persuade the people. But there are so many other functions and roles that the media plays. Media plays the most important role in the process of socialization, localization, and globalization of issues and subject matter. Media transfers cultural values and traditions. Media is monitor of society. It is said to be the watchdog of Society. The surveillance function of media also is considered as very important. Media transfers and transforms the values, traditions and belief systems

by winning the hearts and minds of its audiences. “Whether or not the world really is getting worse, the nature of news will make us think that it is” (The Guardian, 2023). The statement indicates how media can impact on our thought making. The thoughts and perceptions of the people in society are almost guided by media content. Media as a mediator, teacher, interpreter and advisor serves the people for their well-being and development.

Agenda setting for the public welfare and positive development of the society through disseminating news and views is media’s one of the primary concern. By the way it is found that media sometimes do propaganda, “information, especially of a biased or misleading nature, used to promote a political cause or point of view” (Oxford Languages, 2024). The social agendas are mostly set by media and thus media plays the role for social agenda-setting. Media eradicates the gap between authorities and general public. Therefore, the role of media is to work as a bridge between government, public, private and corporate sectors. Media is called the catalyst for development because the role of media in and for development is highly appreciated. Media raises the voice of the voiceless. The messages related to development are carried by the media and disseminated among the public.

Media also plays a vital role in making the public and authorities aware of their rights and duties. It is mass media which holds all the stakeholders of society accountable making all of them responsible towards society and humanity. If any wrong doing and irregularity takes place or anyone in the power commits any mistake media spreads the information among the mass and warns to stop. “The media exaggerates negative news. This distortion has consequences” (Steven Pinker 2018). Media persuades the people to stand against such wrong doings making the case known among the public audiences. Even media sometimes and most often exaggerates the issues negatively and tries to create negativity. It is because negativity spreads faster and the content goes viral making the media more popular. In such condition people should have proper media literacy so that they can easily examine what is trustworthy fact and how the

information has been exaggerated. So that media can be more responsible for disseminating the exact information without any exaggeration.

Some major **roles of media for strengthening of democracy** can be listed as follows.

- The public sphere for social debate and discourse on social affairs
- The watchdog role
- The voice of the voiceless
- The advocate for public integrity
- Role of surveillance
- Mirror of the society
- Maintaining and promoting peace and harmony
- The role of creating unity in diversity
- The Fourth Estate function
- Driving force for fundamental rights
- A platform for enabling democratic participation
- Media as a social mobilizer
- The role of the promoter
- The role of advisor
- Exposing of the truth
- Demanding responsibility and accountability
- Monitoring role in elections and other democratic process
- Development agent etc.

Media and Democracy in Nepal

“The importance and role of Nepali media is not decreases but its duties and responsibilities is increased. For a democratic society to flourish a wider public sphere is needed, where all sort of the views is discoursed and discussed, only the neutral and professional media can provide this space” (Gautam, 2080). There is a relationship of reciprocity between media and democracy as the history has shown. The role and function of media in and for democracy can not be underestimated as one can not virtually sustain without the other. If one is let alone neither we can imagine responsible and professional media nor a healthy and functioning democracy.

While we discuss the relationship between media and democracy in Nepal, both can not be separated from each other as always everywhere. The most prominent modern mass media, Gorakhapatra, the first daily newspaper of the country, came into existence during the authoritarian Rana regime, around fifty years earlier democracy was officially declared in 1951. Although media at that time was governed and fully controlled by authoritarian rulers, existing media, including Gorakhapatra would be engaged in informing the people, ensuring the people's right to information, education, and entertainment. We can say that it paved the way for and also instilled the need and will for democracy among Nepali people. When after decades-long collective struggle and revolution by people saw the downfall of the century-long autocratic Rana regime in 1951, existing media run in different parts of the country or outside had played a crucial role in overthrowing the 104-year-old regime.

The arrival of democracy saw the wave of development of media. For the first time, books, newspapers and magazines as well as other alternative forms of mass media could publish and sustain freely. In turn, the media sector shouldered responsibility to contribute for the strengthening of the newly established democracy.

With time mass media was marching towards its professional maturity, and its progress came to a halt when Nepal's democracy was snatched with King Mahendra imposing a partyless Panchayat system. When the autocratic Panchayat system started ruling the country taking away democracy, media development was barricaded and the free and favourable environment required for the growth of media had massively shrunk. Those media, journalists and communicators who heaped praise for the king and the Panchayat system could sustain as there was no space for raising questions against the system, seeking accountability and keeping a check on the anti-democratic political system of the country. Those who couldn't blindly support the ruler and the ruling system had to face threats, lose their jobs and even be jailed. Many newspapers, magazines and press were closed.

Many journalists who could not compromise their professional integrity were imprisoned.

With several forms of struggles, strikes and revolutionised with collective force of political parties, people, students and media as well as other internal and external enforcement it took another three decades. Missions against the panchayat system marched all over the country for the restoration of democracy. After the then-ruler King Birendra felt that majority of the Nepali people were not happy with Panchayat and wanted democracy, the thirty yearlong authoritarian Panchayat regime fell and democracy was re-established. Although there was the malpractice of partisan press, the role of Nepali media in the restoration of democracy was very important. Nepali media even being biased aided the revolution against the Panchayat dictatorship in the name of mission journalism. It was the media's active participation in the restoration of democracy. In return, democracy and once again favourable environment, which was enshrined in the Constitution as the right to freedom of expression, press freedom, and right to information supported the rise and growth of media development the country had never seen before.

The Maoist armed conflict, which started in 1996, gave another massive blow to the media sector and curtailed the practising of freedom of expression as guaranteed in the constitution. Once again, the media and journalists were under threat and were attacked for doing their duty. Even many of the journalists were murdered, kidnapped, and mutilated and their properties were seized and damaged. However, this was not only from the Maoist side but also done by the state. Most of the fundamental democratic, civic and constitutional rights were seized by the government itself in the name of insurgency. The force revolutionising against the state also pushed media, journalists and all the people in the country into a harsh terrifying life threatening age.

At the time the country as a whole was living under constant threat, there was no question of rights and democracy. Even amidst the fear of life and threat, many media stood on their

ground and played a pivotal role in information dissemination and making people aware of the negative impact of conflict, war and terrorism. The media raised the voices of people for the end of the war and for maintaining social peace and harmony. They struggled for the protection and promotion of democracy as well as ensuring rights given to the citizens by the Constitution.

When King Gyanendra started his direct autocratic rule dissolving the parliament, and curtailing many of the democratic rights, including, directly controlling media and its content, the situation exacerbated for media and democracy because of the ruler's dictatorship. Despite all these challenges and the hostile environment for media and democracy, the media encouraged the people as well as other parties to continually press for ensuring democratic rights and claiming press freedom. Media owners and journalists were once again threatened and jailed for doing their job as they came to the streets along with political parties and civil society members, voicing against the autocratic rules of King Gyanendra.

As the king realised that a vast majority of Nepali people were struggling against his rule and supporting the movement led by seven political parties, along with the Maoist party, he relinquished his direct rule and restored the House of Representatives. The media's role in the reattainment of democracy during this period was highly appreciated. Kantipur Daily, the largest-selling newspaper in Nepal, was even given the accolade of being the '8th Party' as it was struggling against the King's rule along with the Seven Party Alliance of the time.

It can be stated confidently that media played a crucial role in settling the armed conflict and facilitating the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Accord (CPA). It also contributed significantly to the betterment of democracy through timely and fair elections. The media were instrumental during the drafting and promulgation of the Interim Constitution of 2007 and its implementation, and pressed for fostering democratic values in what was called a 'New Nepal'.

During the constituent assembly elections and the

constitution-making process, the media played vital role in informing and persuading the public about the democratic process, promoting and enhancing participatory democracy. The media's surveillance and watchdog functions ensured that the recent constitution was a strong and respected document. They raised both their voices and the voices of the public during the drafting of legal and constitutional provisions. As a result, the commitment to democracy and complete press freedom is enshrined in the preamble of the Constitution of Nepal 2015.

The Way Forward: Promote Media Literacy for Strengthening of Democracy

It can be an overstatement if we assume that the role of media in a democracy is always perfect or it always does its job in the best way possible. In today's democratic societies, media outlets are proliferating, and their regulation and self-regulation are not always guaranteed. Instances of misinformation and disinformation are prevalent more than ever, not just in online media but also in traditional and mainstream media. These platforms sometimes disseminate fake news and engage in various forms of propaganda.

Partisanship has led to media biases, and the neutrality and credibility of media are often questioned. Many media outlets carry personal, political, corporate, and other vested interests, being owned by political leaders, parties, corporate businessmen, and others compromising with their professionalism and ethics. Critics, experts, media students, researchers, and audiences frequently point out that the media lacks professionalism and ignores the principles of news and journalism. Media content often lacks accuracy, balance, and credibility. Concerns about truthfulness, bias, fairness, and objectivity are significant.

Media owners, journalists, and other professionals sometimes disregard codes of conduct and ethical considerations. Media platforms can become venues for hate speech, defamation, and libel. Instead of acting as watchdogs, many media platforms serve as "lapdogs," promoting the interests of their investors and

donors as we have seen in the case of Indian media during the Modi government and some media moguls. Media should be the voice of the voiceless but are often turned out to be the mouthpieces of their patrons, those in power and their owners.

As vital components of democracy, media must play a crucial role in fostering democratic values. They should enable public participation in democratic processes, advocate for public well-being, and create informed citizens who seek and demand good governance. Media should make the general public and people in the power aware of their rights and duties. They should work towards maintaining peace and harmony in society, promoting inclusive involvement and participation in democratic and developmental activities. Media can thus help unify diverse and pluralistic societies.

In addition to the media's responsibilities for promoting a just and democratic society, media literacy among the public is equally crucial. To understand the intent meaning of news, the readers should have higher level of media literacy. "Media literacy is the ability of a citizen to access, analyze, and produce information for specific outcome." (The Aspen Institute, 2023).

To be a media literate audience (reader, listener and viewer) one must be able to understand, analyze, evaluate different types of media and the message they are sending (study.com, 2023). "Media literacy is not just important, it's absolutely critical. It's going to make the difference between whether kids are a tool of the mass media or whether the mass media is a tool for kids to use" (Linda Ellerbee, 2016). No matter how independently and professionally the media act, if the audiences are not well aware of how media operates, its biases and how it can intentionally compromise with its principles, the media are still bound to fall short of its duties and making citizens informed. In the absence of media literacy, citizens can easily fail in distinguishing the right information from the fake one, truth from partial one; and factual news and views from propaganda.

Media literacy equips individuals with the skills to critically evaluate media content, recognize biases, and differentiate between

credible information and misinformation. By promoting media literacy, society can better understand and engage with media content, making more informed decisions. Oxford Language Dictionary defines media literacy as 'the ability to critically analyse stories presented in the mass media and to determine their accuracy or credibility' (Oxford Languages, 2024). As this meaning denotes media literacy actually is the idea, skill, ability or capacity of a media audience for finding out what is factual and truthful information and what is not that is disseminated as new or other content by media. People having media literacy have the ability to access, obtain, understand, analyze, verify, produce and share the media content using their own idea.

“.....the ability of a citizen to access, analyze, and produce information for specific outcomes” (The Aspen Institute, 2010) is known as media literacy. That means information is the most primary function of mass media that is why media literacy cannot be separately complete without information literacy. So, UNESCO introduces media and information literacy in a combined way as, “MIL constitutes a composite set of knowledge, skills, attitudes, competencies and practices that allow effectively access, analyze, critically evaluate, interpret, use, create and disseminate information and media products with the use of existing means and tools on a creative, legal and ethical basis It is an integral part of so-called “21st century skills” or “transversal competencies” (UNESCO, 2024).

But media literacy among Nepali readers to perfectly analyses and differentiate the news contents as positive, negative and neutral is always questioned. As media are found time and again to distort the information, select the news angle unnecessarily positively or negatively missing neutrality and the tendency is said to be more in newspapers and the need of media literacy is increasing day by day.

“The illiterate of the 21st century will not be those who cannot read and write, but those who cannot learn, unlearn, and relearn” (Alvin Toffler, 2016). Media literacy strengthens democracy by empowering citizens to hold media accountable demand

higher standards of journalism and adhere to professional ethics. Educated audiences are less likely to be swayed by fake news or propaganda and are better prepared to participate in democratic processes compared to those uneducated citizens or those who are not media literate. As a result, media literacy initiatives should be integrated into educational systems and community programs to ensure widespread understanding and engagement. This should be a joint responsibility of the media industry as well as the government and state bodies like the Press Council, and the Department of Information and Broadcasting among others that work to protect freedom of expression and other democratic rights.

As the watchdog of society and the fourth estate, the media must seek responsibility and accountability from others while being accountable and responsible for themselves. To protect and promote democracy and enable participatory democracy, the media must first exemplify responsibility and accountability. Before questioning others' wrongdoings, the media must be professional, fair, trustworthy, and neutral. Raising public awareness against crime, corruption, and irregularities requires the media to avoid misinformation and disinformation and refrain from being a tool of propaganda.

By fostering media literacy and adhering to high standards of journalism, the media can better serve as a pillar of democracy. Together, professional media and their responsible practices and an informed public can contribute to strengthening democratic values and processes, ensuring a healthier, more transparent, and more equitable society for all.

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